

Tourism Product Development Strategy (Study on the Botubarani Whale Shark Tourism Object, Bone Bolango Regency)

Andi Yusniar Mendo¹, Syamsul B. Biki², Rosna Musa³, Arif Afriyanto Yasin²

^{1,2,3,4}Management Study Program, Faculty of Economics, Universitas Negeri Gorontalo, Gorontalo, Indonesia

Abstract:- This study aims to determine the strategy for developing tourism products at the Whale Shark Tourism Object in Botubarani Village, as well as what alternative strategies are proposed to be implemented. This research is important for the Tourism Awareness Group (POKDARWIS) as the manager of tourism objects and becomes a study material in implementing tourism product development strategies in these tourist destinations. This type of research is qualitative with source triangulation method. Data collection techniques were carried out by interviewing and filling out questionnaires on selected informants based on aspects related to tourism product development strategies. Analysis of the data used is descriptive analysis using the SWOT (strength, weakness, opportunity, threat) analysis method. The results of the analysis show that Botubarani Whale Shark Tourism is located in quadrant I on the Cartesian Diagram which has a good value weight in the organization's internal factors, namely strengths and external factors, namely opportunities. This has the power to take advantage of existing opportunities (Growth oriented strategy). Alternative development strategies that are in accordance with the existing situation, the researcher recommends 3 alternative development strategies obtained from the combination of Strength and Opportunities, namely: (1) Increasing promotion and improving development programs to better attract visitors so that they are ready to face competition between tourist objects (2) Coordinating with the private sector and government to invest in tourism development (3) Increasing tourism promotion through social media.

Keywords:- Whale Shark; SWOT analysis; Development Strategy.

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of the world of tourism is marked by the increasing number of tourist visits from year to year. According to UNWTO Tourism Towards 2030, the number of international tourist arrivals worldwide is expected to increase by 3.3% per year during the period 2010 to 2030 (UNWTO,

2016). Indonesia's tourism competitiveness index ranking in the world rose to 40th in 2019 from 42nd in 2017. This is based on The Travel & Tourism Competitiveness Report released by the WEF (World Economic Forum) 2019 recently. In the world, Indonesia is ranked 40th out of 140 countries. In Southeast Asia, Indonesia's tourism competitiveness index is ranked fourth. Indonesia received a score of 4.3 from the total assessment of pillars such as the business environment, security, health and hygiene, human resources and employment, environmental sustainability and others. The rating scale is 1 for the worst while 7 for the best. A score above 5 obtained by Indonesia is a tourism priority. The hygiene pillar is one of the improvements made by Indonesia and is considered good. In 2015, Indonesia was ranked 50th in the world. In 2017, Indonesia's ranking jumped to rank 42. Meanwhile, the Indonesian government is targeting to rise to rank 30 in the world. Regarding foreign exchange, the contribution from the tourism sector continues to increase every year. The existing tourism potentials can also create an attractive market to be developed and researched, so that the role of tourism in the business industry will become an asset that must be utilized optimally through tourism. This can be aimed at increasing national income and regional income in order to increase the prosperity of the community. In addition to providing equal distribution of business opportunities for the community, tourism can also create employment opportunities, then absorb labor so as to reduce the number of unemployed.

In Indonesia, the tourism industry is currently one of the income sectors that has an impact on a region or a country. One of them is tourism in Gorontalo Province, namely whale shark tourism in Botubarani Village, Kabila Bone District, Bone Bolango Regency. The behavior of whale sharks in the waters of Gorontalo, especially Botubarani, has its own characteristics and charm. This is because the number of whale sharks is not small, which is approximately 17 individuals (WSI, 2016 in Kasim., et.al, 2016). The journey to the location is about 12 kilometers from downtown Gorontalo. It can be reached by car in about 20 minutes. Whale shark tourism has become one of the popular tourist destinations and is in demand by tourists.

No	Year	Domestic Tourist	Foreign Tourist	Number of Visitors
1	2016	24.03	8.013	32.043
2	2017	11.63	193	11.823
3	2018	16.847	1.51	18.357
4	2019	10.772	1.693	12.465
5	2020	945	348	1.293

Table 1:- Number of Visitors to Botubarani Whale Shark Tourism 2016 – 2020

Source: Tourism, Youth and Sports Office of Bone Bolango Regency

Berdasarkan tabel di atas jumlah pengunjung wisata hiu paus Botubarani dari tahun 2016 hingga 2020 tercatat mengalami fluktuasi. Apalagi di tahun 2020 terjadi pandemi Covid-19 hampir di seluruh dunia yang membuat sektor pariwisata dunia termasuk Indonesia begitu terpuak akibat menurun drastisnya jumlah kunjungan wisatawan sebagai akibat ditutupnya akses keluar masuk antar negara termasuk akses dari dan ke daerah di wilayah nusantara. Pengelola wisata hiu paus yaitu Pokdarwis (Kelompok Sadar Wisata) di Desa Botubarani mempunyai tugas berat untuk tetap menjalankan pengelolaan obyek wisata hiu paus, karena penurunan jumlah kunjungan wisatawan tersebut sangat mempengaruhi pemasukan yang diterima dari obyek wisata, mengingat posisi strategis obyek wisata hiu paus yang merupakan salah satu destinasi wisata andalan di kabupaten Bone Bolango.

Maka atas hal-hal tersebut peneliti tertarik untuk mengadakan penelitian tentang bagaimana strategi pengembangan produk wisata hiu paus botubarani. Strategi pengembangan produk pariwisata sangat diperlukan mengingat besarnya potensi pariwisata obyek wisata hiu paus yang belum dioptimalkan. Pengelola obyek wisata diharapkan untuk dapat mengoptimalkan potensi obyek wisata sehingga memiliki nilai jual yang tinggi. Berdasarkan latar belakang diatas maka penulis tertarik untuk melakukan penelitian dengan judul “Strategi Pengembangan Wisata Hiu Paus (Studi pada obyek wisata hiu paus di Desa Botubarani Kabupaten Bone Bolango)”

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Tourism

In Law Number 10 of 2009 concerning Tourism, tourism is a variety of tourism activities and is supported by various facilities and services provided by the community, entrepreneurs, the Government, and Regional Governments. According to Meyers (2009) in Suwena Ketut (2017) tourism is a travel activity that is carried out temporarily from the original place of residence to the destination area for reasons not to settle or earn a living but only to have fun, fulfill curiosity, spend leisure time or make a living. holidays and other purposes. According to Musanef (1995) in Primadany, Mardiyono, and Riyanto (2009) tourism is a trip that is carried out for a while, which is carried out from one place to another to enjoy sightseeing and recreational trips. From the definitions above, it can be concluded that tourism is an activity carried out by humans which is temporary or not permanent to enjoy tourist trips.

B. Product of Tourism

According to Suwanto (2004) tourism products are all services that are obtained and felt or enjoyed by tourists since leaving their place of residence, to their chosen tourist destination and returning to their home where they originally departed. Kotler and Armstrong (2008) in Kurniasih (2013) state that a product is something that can be offered to the market so that people are attracted to it, want to acquire, use it and consume it to fulfill their wants or needs. Kodhyat (2007) in Kurniasih (2013) states that tourism products are everything that tourists are interested in and bought to enjoy. According to Middleton (2001) in Martina (2013) there are three main components of tourism products, namely attractions, amenities/facilities, and accessibility.

C. Development Strategy

According to Chandler (1962) in Rangkuti (2016) strategy is a tool to achieve company goals in relation to long-term goals, follow-up programs, and resource allocation priorities. Moekidjat (2005:20) in Ervina (2017) development is a change made by a person or group to lead to improvement and that change must be based on knowledge, skills and attitudes that are embodied in work for now and for the future. According to Rangkuti (2016), a good understanding of the concept of strategy and other related concepts will determine the success of the strategy being prepared. The concepts are as follows:

➤ Distinctive Competence

Distinctive Competence is an action taken by a company in order to perform activities better than its competitors. According to Day and Wensley (1988) in Rangkuti (2016), the identification of distinctive competence in an organization includes workforce expertise and resource capabilities.

➤ Competitive Advantage

Competitive advantage is a specific activity developed by a company to be superior to its competitors. According to Porter (in Rangkuti 2016), there are three strategies that companies can do to gain competitive advantage, namely:

• Cost Leadership

If the company can get a higher competitive advantage compared to its competitors if it can provide a selling price that is cheaper than the price given by its competitors with the same product value/quality. The company can achieve a lower selling price because it takes advantage of economies of scale, production efficiency, use of technology, ease of access, and so on.

• *Differentiation Strategies (Differentiation Strategies)*

If the combination of small or narrow competitive targets is combined with product differentiation, the company must focus on product diversity. Product differentiation strategy (Differentiation), encourages companies to be able to find their own uniqueness in the target market. The uniqueness of the product (goods or service) that is put forward allows a company to attract the greatest interest from its potential consumers.

III. METHOD

The type of research carried out is a case study, where the results of this study only apply to the location where the research is carried out. Researchers use case study research because they want to know the actual situation that occurs in an object by providing a clear and complete picture. The object studied in this study is the strategy of developing whale shark tourism products in Botubarani Village, Bone Bolango Regency.

A. Data Analysis

To answer the first problem formulation "What is the strategy for developing whale shark tourism products in Bone Bolango district" descriptive analysis is carried out by:

- Describe the results of interviews and questionnaires related to the development strategy used in whale shark tourism in Bone Bolango Regency.
- Classifying the strategies chosen by the Whale Shark Tourism Manager. Classification is done by grouping the same strategy options into one group based on data obtained from interviews and questionnaires.

- Analyze the choice of strategy and the reasons for choosing the strategy for each category of questions on the development of whale shark tourism products by calculating the percentage for each strategy choice (the value of each strategy chosen by each respondent is added up and then divided by the number of respondents, multiplied by 100. The higher the percentage for each choice of strategy indicates the greater the strategy chosen or used by the botubarani whale shark attraction).
- Summarizing the results of the analysis of the choice of development strategy and the reasons for choosing the development strategy by giving a percentage to each respondent (summing up the three categories of strategies for each respondent).

In relation to the second problem formulation, "What alternative tourism product development strategy is more suitable with the existing situation in Botubarani whale shark tourism based on a SWOT analysis?". In this study, a SWOT analysis was carried out to determine alternative development strategies by:

- Identify the strengths (internal factors) and opportunities (external factors) that exist in Botubarani whale shark tourism.
- Analyze SWOT. This analysis is carried out by determining the internal factors (strengths-weaknesses) and external factors (opportunities-threats) that exist in Botubarani whale shark tourism.
- Summarize the results of the SWOT analysis by compiling IFAS (Internal Factor Analysis Summary) and EFAS (External Factor Analysis Summary) tables.
- The following is an example of the IFAS and EFAS table used by researchers along with the criteria for filling out the table;

Internal Factor	Weight	Rating	Weight x Rating
Strength	✓	✓	✓
Weakness	✓	✓	✓
Total	✓	✓	✓

Table 2:- IFAS
Source: Rangkuti (2016)

- Determine the factors that are the company's strengths and weaknesses in column 1.
- Give each factor a weight on a scale from 1.0 (most important) to 0.0 (not important), based on the influence of these factors on the company's strategic position. (All these weights must not exceed the total score of 1.00)
- Calculate the rating (in column 3) for each factor by giving a scale ranging from 4 (outsanding) to 1 (poor), based on the influence of these factors on the condition of the company concerned. Positive variables (all variables that fall into the strength category) are scored from +1 to +4 (very good) by comparing them with the industry average or with the main competitors. While the variables that are negative, the opposite. For example, if the company's weaknesses are large compared to the industry average, the

score is 1, whereas if the company's weaknesses are below the industry average, the score is 4.

- Multiply the weight in column 2 by the rating in column 3, to obtain the weighting factor in column 4. The result is a weighting score for each factor whose value varies from 4.0 (outsanding) to 1.0 (poor).
- Use column 5 to provide comments or notes why certain factors were chosen, and how their weighted scores were calculated.
- Add up the weighting scores (in column 4), to obtain the total weighting score for the company concerned. This total value shows how a particular company reacts to its internal strategic factors. This total score can be used to compare this company with other companies in the same industry group.

External Factor	Weight	Rating	Weight x Rating
Opportunity	✓	✓	✓
Threat	✓	✓	✓
Total	✓	✓	✓

Table 3:- EFAS
Source: Rangkuti (2016)

- Arrange in column 1 (5 to 10 opportunities and threats).
- Give each factor a weight in column 2, starting from 1.0 (very important) to 0.0 (not important). These factors are likely to have an impact on strategic factors.
- Calculate the rating (in column 3) for each factor by giving a scale ranging from 4 (outsanding) to 1 (poor) based on the influence of these factors on the condition of the company concerned. The rating value for the opportunity factor is positive (a bigger chance is given a +4 rating, but if the opportunity is small, it is given a +1 rating). Giving a threat rating value is the opposite. For example, if the threat value is very large, the rating is 1. Conversely, if the threat value is low, the rating is 4.
- Multiply the weight in column 2 by the rating in column 3, to obtain the weighting factor in the column. The result is a weighted score for each factor whose value varies from 4.0 (outsanding) to 1.0 (poor).
- Use column 5 to provide comments or notes why certain factors were chosen and how their weighted scores were calculated.
- Add up the weighting scores (in column 4), to obtain the total weighting score for the company concerned. This total value shows how a particular company reacts to its external strategic factors. This total score can be used to compare this company with other companies in the same industry group.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Profile of Botubarani Whale Shark Tourist Attractions

Botubarani is one of the villages located right facing Tomini Bay. This village is included in the Kabilabone District, Bone Bolango Regency, Gorontalo Province. The location is 20-30 minutes from the city. Most of the population in Botubarani Village make a living as traditional fishermen (Figure 5) with a boat mode of no more than 2 GT (gross tonnage). The common boat propulsion engine used is a ketinting engine outboard motor with a power of not more than 4000 rpm. Local fishermen catch fish by fishing and casting nets. Some fishermen who operate at night use light-producing devices (lights) to facilitate the fishing process.

B. The Development Strategy Used by POKDARWIS in Botubarani Village

The strategy carried out by the Tourism Awareness Group (POKDARWIS) is divided into 3 major parts, namely:

- Watching Tour, in this tour, visitors use boats as a medium for the appearance of whale sharks, this spot is chosen by tourists who cannot swim or do not want to get wet when interacting with whale sharks
- Swimming/surface diving (snorkeling), visitors can clearly see whale sharks in the water so that it becomes a special impression for tourists
- Diving tourism (diving), this tour is especially for divers who already have a certificate using tubes/scuba diving. This spot has a different sensation because you can see the whole whale

C. IFE (Internal Factor Evaluation) analysis

Internal Strategy Factor		Weight	Rating	Score
Strength				
S1	Whale Shark attractions have a top attraction	0,08	5	0,4146
S2	Whale Shark attraction safety is conducive	0,08	5	0,4146
S3	Whale shark tourism product development plan/program is prepared and implemented annually	0,07	5	0,3780
S4	Whale Shark tourism promotion through electronic media and the internet	0,09	5	0,4512
S5	Mileage of tourist attractions that are close to the capital city of Gorontalo Province	0,08	5	0,4268
S6	Availability of adequate transportation to tourist sites	0,08	5	0,4390
S7	Relatively low cost	0,08	5	0,4390
		0,59		2,96
Weakness				
W1	Whale Sharks sometimes don't appear on the surface of the beach	0,07	5	0,3780
W2	Tourism object development program that is still simple	0,07	5	0,3658

W3	Limited budget for the cost of facilities and infrastructure	0,06	5	0,3414
W4	Lack of public awareness in efforts to develop tourism objects	0,06	4	0,2439
W5	Lack of quantity and quality of souvenir items sold	0,06	4	0,2439
W6	Product diversification and packaging of tourist attractions is still simple	0,068	4	0,2731
				1,84
		1		1,11

Table 4:- IFAS
Source: Data Processed (2022)

After analyzing and identifying the internal environmental conditions in the form of strengths and weaknesses, here are the results of the analysis:

- Strength is everything that is needed in conditions that are internal to the organization so that organizational activities run optimally. Strength is also used to capture existing opportunities. Based on the results of the researcher's observations and interviews with the Pokdarwis Chair, information that supports the development of the Botubarani Whale Shark is obtained:
 - Whale Shark attractions have excellent attractions
 - Whale Shark attraction safety is conducive
 - Whale shark tourism product development plans/programs are prepared and implemented annually
 - Promotion of Whale Shark tourism through electronic media and the internet
 - Mileage of tourist attractions close to the capital city of Gorontalo Province

- Availability of adequate transportation to tourist sites
- Relatively low cost
- Weaknesses are limitations or deficiencies in resources, skills, and capabilities that effectively hinder the company's performance. Based on the results of the researcher's observations and interviews with the Pokdarwis Chair, information that supports the development of the Botubarani Whale Shark is obtained:
 - Whale Sharks sometimes do not appear on the beach surface
 - The tourism object development program is still simple
 - Limited budget for the cost of facilities and infrastructure
 - Lack of public awareness in efforts to develop tourism objects
 - Lack of quantity and quality of souvenirs sold
 - Product diversification and packaging of tourist attractions are still simple

D. EFE (External Factor Evaluation) analysis

External Strategy Factor		Weight	Rating	Score
Opportunity				
O1	Easy level of accessibility	0,12	5	0,6319
O2	The number of visitors	0,11	5	0,5947
O3	Increasing tourism products and attractions by utilizing existing potentials	0,13	5	0,6505
O4	Cooperation with other parties in the development of tourist attractions and facilities and infrastructure	0,12	5	0,6133
O5	Whale Shark tourism support infrastructure development	0,11	5	0,5762
Threat				
T1	There are other tourist attractions that have sprung up	0,08	4	0,3420
T2	Unpredictable weather	0,08	3	0,2453
T3	Government regulations	0,07	3	0,211
T4	Lack of awareness of tourists to maintain tourism objects	0,07	3	0,2230
T5	There is no cooperation with the private sector for the development of tourism objects	0,07	3	0,2230
				12,453
		1		1,82

Table 5:- EFAS
Source: Data processed (2022)

After analyzing and identifying the external environmental conditions in the form of threats and opportunities, the following are the results of the analysis:

- Opportunities are important situations that are profitable in a company environment. Important trends are one source of opportunities, such as technological changes and increasing relationships between companies and buyers or suppliers are a picture of opportunities for companies. Based on the results of the researcher's observations and interviews with the Pokdarwis Chair, information that supports the development of the Botubarani Whale Shark is obtained:
 - Easy level of accessibility
 - The number of visitors
 - Increasing tourism products and attractions by utilizing existing potentials
- Weaknesses are limitations or deficiencies in resources, skills, and capabilities that effectively hinder the company's performance. These limitations can be in the form of facilities, financial resources, management

capabilities and marketing skills that can be a source of company weaknesses. Based on the results of the researcher's observations and interviews with the Pokdarwis Chair, information that supports the development of the Botubarani Whale Shark is obtained:

- There are other tourist attractions that have sprung up
- Unpredictable weather
- Government regulations
- Lack of awareness of tourists to maintain tourism objects
- There is no cooperation with the private sector for the development of tourism objects

Then the table difference is calculated for the results of the analysis of internal factors and the results of the analysis of external factors, where for internal factors of 1.11 and external factors of 1.82, the coordinates of the SWOT diagram are (1.11; 1.82). Based on this difference, coordinates are determined to clearly see how the position of the Botubarani Whale Shark tourism quadrant is as can be seen in the Cartesian diagram image below:

Fig 1:- Cartesian chart (Source: Data processed, 2022)

Based on the picture, it can be seen that Botubarani Whale Shark Tourism is located in quadrant I which has a good value weight in internal organizational factors, namely strengths and external factors, namely opportunities. have the power to take advantage of existing opportunities (Growth oriented strategy)

E. SWOT Analysis

SWOT is an acronym for Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats from the company's external environment. According to Jogiyanto (2005:46), SWOT is used to assess the strengths and weaknesses of the company's resources and external opportunities and challenges faced.

According to David (Fred R. David, 2008,8), All organizations have strengths and weaknesses in the functional areas of business. No company is equally strong or weak in all areas of business. Internal strengths/weaknesses, combined with external opportunities/threats and a clear mission statement, form the basis for setting goals and strategies. Goals and strategies are set with the intention of leveraging internal strengths and overcoming weaknesses. Based on the SWOT matrix, four main strategies can be drawn up, namely; SO, WO, ST, WT. Each of these strategies has its own characteristics and should be implemented in the next strategy implemented together and mutually support each other.

<p>IFE</p> <p>EFE</p>	<p>Strengths (S)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Objek wisata Hiu Paus mempunyai daya tarik unggulan Keamanan objek wisata Hiu Paus kondusif Rencana/program pengembangan produk wisata hiu paus disusun dan dilaksanakan tiap tahun Promosi wisata Hiu Paus melalui media elektronik dan internet Jarak tempuh obyek wisata yang dekat dengan ibukota Provinsi Gorontalo Tersedianya transportasi yang memadai ke lokasi wisata Biaya yang relatif murah 	<p>Weakness (S)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Ikan Hiu Paus kadang-kadang tidak muncul di permukaan pantai Program pengembangan Obyek wisata yang masih sederhana Keterbatasan anggaran untuk biaya sarana dan prasarana Kurangnya kesadaran masyarakat dalam upaya pengembangan obyek wisata Kurangnya kuantitas dan kualitas barang-barang cinderamata yang dijual Diversifikasi produk dan pengemasan daya tarik wisata masih sederhana
<p>Opportunity</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Tingkat aksesibilitas yang mudah Banyaknya wisatawan yang berkunjung Peningkatan produk dan atraksi wisata dengan memanfaatkan potensi-potensi yang ada Kerjasama dengan pihak lainnya dalam pengembangan atraksi wisata serta sarana dan prasarana Pengembangan infrastruktur pendukung wisata Hiu Paus 	<p>Strategi SO</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Meningkatkan promosi dan memperbaiki program pengembangan lebih bagus untuk menarik pengunjung sehingga siap untuk menghadapi persaingan antar objek wisata Melakukan koordinasi dengan pihak swasta dan pemerintahan untuk menanamkan modal Peningkatan promosi pariwisata melalui media sosial media 	<p>Strategi WO</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Pengembangan wisata berbasis festival budaya dan tradisi secara rutin Meningkatkan kemampuan dan pengetahuan SDM Pariwisata mengenai Sadar Wisata dan Sapta Pesona Menyediakan inovasi produk yang sedang tren terkait cinderamata
<p>Threats</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Adanya tempat wisata lain yang bermunculan Cuaca yang sulit diprediksi Makin banyaknya peraturan pemerintah Kurangnya kesadaran wisatawan untuk menjaga obyek wisata Belum adanya kerjasama dengan pihak swasta terhadap pengembangan obyek wisata 	<p>Strategi ST</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Mengoptimalkan potensi alam dan keunikan objek wisata dengan mempertahankan dan pemeliharaan objek wisata secara berkesinambungan untuk menghadapi persaingan antar objek wisata. Pengembangan dan pembangunan objek wisata yang ramah lingkungan dengan melakukan kontrol yang tegas terhadap pelaksanaan unsur-unsur pelaku wisata yang tidak sesuai dengan sikap dan tindakan pelaku wisata yang dapat mengancam kerusakan objek wisata 	<p>Strategi WT</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Peningkatan kualitas tenaga kerja professional dalam pengelolaan dan pemeliharaan objek wisata secara berkesinambungan sehingga mengurangi kerusakan lingkungan. Melakukan pengawasan dan pemeliharaan fasilitas-fasilitas yang telah ada dilokasi objek wisata.

Table 6:- Botubarani Whale Shark Tourism Development Strategy
Source: Data processed (2022)

Strategies that can be carried out in developing the Botubarani Whale Shark Tourism Object are as follows:

➤ *S-O Strategy (Strength and Opportunities)*

The S-O strategy is a strategy that optimizes strengths to take advantage of opportunities (Opportunities), the alternatives to the S-O strategy are as follows:

- Increase promotions and improve development programs to better attract visitors so that they are ready to face competition between tourist objects
- Coordinate with the private sector and government to invest in tourism development
- Increasing tourism promotion through social media

➤ *W-O Strategy (Weakness and Opportunities)*

W-O strategy is a strategy that minimizes weaknesses (Weaknesses) by taking advantage of opportunities (Opportunities), alternatives to W-O are as follows: Development of tourism based on cultural and traditional festivals on a regular basis

- Increase the ability and knowledge of Tourism HR regarding Tourism Awareness and Sapta Pesona
- Providing trending product innovations related to souvenirs

➤ *S-T Strategy (Strength and Treats)*

The ST strategy is a strategy that uses strength (strength) to overcome threats (treats) are as follows:

- Optimizing the natural potential and uniqueness of tourism objects by maintaining and maintaining tourism objects on an ongoing basis to face competition between tourist objects.
- Development and construction of eco-friendly tourism objects by exercising firm control over the implementation of elements of tourism actors that are not in accordance with the attitudes and actions of tourism actors that can threaten the destruction of tourism objects.

➤ *W-T Strategies (Weakness and Treats)*

The W-T strategy is a strategy that minimizes weaknesses (weaknesses) and avoids threats (treats) as follows:

- Improving the quality of professional workforce in the management and maintenance of tourism objects on an ongoing basis so as to reduce environmental damage.
- Supervise and maintain existing facilities at tourist attraction locations.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research on the tourism development strategy of the Botubarani Whale Shark as follows:

- Botubarani Whale Shark Tourism is located in quadrant I which has a good value weight in internal organizational factors, namely strengths and external factors, namely opportunities. existing opportunities (Growth oriented strategy)
- Alternative development strategies that are in accordance with the existing situation, the researcher recommends 3 alternative development strategies obtained from the combination of Strengths and Opportunities, namely:
 - Increase promotions and improve development programs to better attract visitors so that they are ready to face competition between tourist objects
 - Coordinate with the private sector and government to invest in tourism development
 - Increasing tourism promotion through social media

RECOMMENDATION

➤ *For Botubarani Whale Shark Pokdarwis*

Suggestions for Pokdarwis Whale Shark Botubarani to be able to apply alternative strategies in developing tourism products based on the results of a SWOT analysis of internal and external strategic factors

➤ *For Further Researchers*

Suggestions for further researchers, so that researchers go deeper to explore information related to development strategies that are in accordance with the situation or place of research, besides that researchers also add relevant respondents to expand information in depth

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